

NDE of GR/EP Composite Parts for Commercial Airplane

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ABSTRACT

A description of the production methods for large commercial Airplane components in Gr/Ep is given together with that of the NDI systems. Types of recurrent defects, their limit of acceptance, are described for the two main fabrication processes, i.e. cocure and secondary bonding.

Some cases history are presented and their evaluation is discussed in detail i.e. full evaluation of highly septumized structures with H/c spliced. Surface condition of same parts is examined with respect to the inspectability of the part. Ultrasonic (through transmission with water coupling, contact pulse echo, low frequency ultrasonics) and Radiographic methods are described in detail with particular emphasis on their complementarity in the full evaluation of production parts.

A method to determine the lay-up order on cured parts is presented in theory and practice using ultrasonic approaches.

